

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.1992 Max: 63.6359	1218 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	589-594

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 693 ✓ Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: Debris Layer (mainly) within Room 3 Covered by XSU: 1016 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are SOIL/MATRIX: clay 20% silt 40% sand ___%

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	Soil/Matrix
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <i>Bronze</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction Color <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Soft <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay) Depth: Original Not Original

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1016	Covers: 1244
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS

SPECIAL FINDS: 203, 202, 205 202: Bottle Stone 203: Bronze Sesterius (coin) 205: miniature Bronze Ladle

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: within room 3, e.g. at the eastern limit of excav. 2010

Shape: the layer is limited by the surrounding walls of room 3

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slight slope to the south

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): no clusters

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): layer is ca. 5cm thick

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

Legend:
 [Hatched] = rocks
 [Wavy] = tufo floor
 [Zigzag] = wall
 [X's] = debris layer (1218)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

layer of debris above tufo floor in room 3
 the same as 1165 and 1158 in rooms 1+2

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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Revised by *CHH*

on *23-7-10*

PDFd by *JJM*

on *27.07.2010*

Entered by

on